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E-GOVERNMENT MATURITY MODELS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Many maturity models have been used to assess or rank e-government portals. In order to assess electronic services provided to the citizens, an appropriate e-government maturity model should be selected. This paper aims at comparing 25 e-government maturity models to find the similarities and differences between them and also to identify their weaknesses and strengths. Although the maturity models present large similarities between them, our findings show that the features included in those models differ from a maturity model to another. Furthermore, while some maturity models are covering some features and introducing new ones, it seems that others are just ignoring them.

KEYWORDS

E-government, portal, maturity model, comparison, best practices, e-services, maturity stages.

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PROGRAM SLICING TECHNIQUES AND ITS APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Program understanding is an important aspect in Software Maintenance and Reengineering. Understanding the program is related to execution behaviour and relationship of variable involved in the program. The task of finding all statements in a program that directly or indirectly influence the value for an occurrence of a variable gives the set of statements that can affect the value of a variable at some point in a program is called a program slice. Program slicing is a technique for extracting parts of computer programs by tracing the programs' control and data flow related to some data item. This technique is applicable in various areas such as debugging, program comprehension and understanding, program integration, cohesion measurement, re-engineering, maintenance, testing where it is useful to be able to focus on relevant parts of large programs. This paper focuses on the various slicing techniques (not limited to) like static slicing, quasi static slicing, dynamic slicing and conditional slicing. This paper also includes various methods in performing the slicing like forward slicing, backward slicing, syntactic slicing and semantic slicing. The slicing of a program is carried out using Java which is a object oriented programming language.

KEYWORDS

Amorphous slicing, Backward slicing, Conditioned slicing, Debugging, Dynamic slicing, Forward slicing, Functional Cohesion, Program Slicing, Quasi Static slicing, Static slicing.

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DESIGNING CODE LEVEL REUSABLE SOFTWARE COMPONENTS

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ABSTRACT

The basic idea behind building Reusable software components is to design interchangeable parts from other industries to the software field of construction. A reuse library or component reuse repository organizes stores and manages reusable components. The biggest advantage of the building reusable software components is that it reduces the time and energy in developing any software. Frameworks provides a standard working system through which user 's main focus is on developing desired modules instead of developing lower level details. By using this facility the software developers can spend more time in developing the requirement of software, rather than preparing the tools of application development. Framework is set of reusable software program that forms the basis for an application. Frameworks help the programmers to build the application quickly .At its best code reuse is accomplished through the sharing of common classes and/or collections of functions, frameworks and procedures. This paper describes how to build the code level reusable components and how to design code level components. Finally providing coding guidelines, standards and best practices used for creating reusable code level components and guidelines and best practices for making configurable and easy to use.

KEYWORDS

Reuse, code, component, barriers, software, framework.

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FORMALIZATION OF THE DATA FLOW DIAGRAM RULES FOR CONSISTENCY CHECK

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ABSTRACT

In system development life cycle (SDLC), a system model can be developed using Data Flow Diagram (DFD). DFD is graphical diagrams for specifying, constructing and visualizing the model of a system. DFD is used in defining the requirements in a graphical view. In this paper, we focus on DFD and its rules for drawing and defining the diagrams. We then formalize these rules and develop the tool based on the formalized rules. The formalized rules for consistency check between the diagrams are used in developing the tool. This is to ensure the syntax for drawing the diagrams is correct and strictly followed. The tool automates the process of manual consistency check between data flow diagrams.

KEYWORDS

Consistency Check, Context Diagram, Data Flow Diagram, Formal Method.

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SOFTWARE METRICS VALIDATION METHODOLOGIES IN SOFTWARE ENGINEERING

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ABSTRACT

In the software measurement validations, assessing the validation of software metrics in software engineering is a very difficult task due to lack of theoretical methodology and empirical methodology [41, 44, 45]. During recent years, there have been a number of researchers addressing the issue of validating software metrics. At present, software metrics are validated theoretically using properties of measures. Further, software measurement plays an important role in understanding and controlling software development practices and products. The major requirement in software measurement is that the measures must represent accurately those attributes they purport to quantify and validation is critical to the success of software measurement. Normally, validation is a collection of analysis and testing activities across the full life cycle and complements the efforts of other quality engineering functions and validation is a critical task in any engineering project. Further, validation objective is to discover defects in a system and assess whether or not the system is useful and usable in operational situation. In the case of software engineering, validation is one of the software engineering disciplines that help build quality into software. The major objective of software validation process is to determine that the software performs its intended functions correctly and provides information about its quality and reliability. This paper discusses the validation methodology, techniques and different properties of measures that are used for software metrics validation. In most cases, theoretical and empirical validations are conducted for software metrics validations in software engineering [1-50].

KEYWORDS

Result Based Software Metrics (RBSM), Software Metrics Validations, Theoretical Validations, Empirical Validations, Software Measurement, Object-Oriented Metrics, Software Engineering

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A NEW APPROACH TO REQUIREMENT ELICITATION BASED ON STAKEHOLDER RECOMMENDATION AND COLLABORATIVE FILTERING

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ABSTRACT

The customers' needs in a software project are identified in the process of Software requirements elicitation. For building a software system this process is considered as one of the most important parts. In this part it is decided precisely what will be built. A close interaction between developers and end-users of the system is needed by requirements' gathering. Meetings can be costly, inconvenient and infrequent if developers and end-users are in different organizations or different cities. The quality of the elicited requirements can greatly be impacted if there is a problem of communication. Requirement elicitation is a process difficult to scale to large software projects with many stakeholders which involves identifying and prioritizing requirements. A stakeholder is an individual or a group who can influence or be influenced by the success or failure of a project. Existing methods to identify and prioritize requirements do not scale well to large projects. Large projects tend to be beset by three problems: information overload, inadequate stakeholder input, and biased prioritization of requirements. Existing methods to identify and prioritize requirements do not scale well to large projects. Existing requirements prioritization methods require substantial efforts from the requirements engineers when there are many requirements. To address the problems Stakeholder recommender model will contain steps:-Identify the large project, Analysis of requirements, Identify and prioritize stakeholders, Predict requirements, Prioritize requirements. For making predictions, our approach will use one of the most well known algorithms that is k-Nearest Neighbor (kNN) algorithm. KNN is used to identify like-minded users with similar rating histories in order to predict ratings for unobserved users-item pairs. A unique subset of the community for each user is found out by KNN by identifying those with similar interests. To do so, every pair of user profile is compared to measure the degree of similarity. A neighbourhood is created for each user by selecting the k most similar users. The similarity between each pair of user profiles for users in the neighbourhood is used to compute predicted ratings.

KEYWORDS

Requirements Elicitation, Stakeholder, k-Nearest Neighbour.

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BAYESIAN NETWORK BASED XP PROCESS MODELLING

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ABSTRACT

A Bayesian Network based mathematical model has been used for modelling Extreme Programming software development process. The model is capable of predicting the expected finish time and the expected defect rate for each XP release. Therefore, it can be used to determine the success/failure of any XP Project. The model takes into account the effect of three XP practices, namely: Pair Programming, Test Driven Development and Onsite Customer practices. The model's predictions were validated against two case studies. Results show the precision of our model especially in predicting the project finish time.

KEYWORDS

Bayesian Networks, Extreme Programming, Process Modelling, Software Process.

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A COMPARISON OF PARAMETER BEST ESTIMATION METHOD FOR SOFTWARE RELIABILITY MODELS

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ABSTRACT

During the past few Decades, many software reliability growth models have been suggested for estimating reliability of software as software reliability growth models. The Functions suggested were non-linear in nature, so it was difficult to estimate the proper parameters. An Estimation method based on Ant Colony Algorithm in which parameters are estimated is discussed in this paper. In this paper, Numerical examples which have been based on five sets of real failure data have been discussed Using existing methods viable solutions for some of the models and data sets cannot be obtained, where as in the proposed method, at least one solution can be obtained. The accuracy of the results using proposed method when compared with PSO algorithm has higher accuracy for at least 10 times for majority of the models.

KEYWORDS

Software Reliability Growth Model, Estimation, Particle Swarm Optimization, Ant Colony Algorithm.

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Survey of maintenance policies for the Last 50 Years

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ABSTRACT

In the past several decades, maintenance and replacement problems have been extensively studied in the literature. Thousands of maintenance and replacement models have been created. However, all these models can fall into some categories of maintenance policies: age replacement policy, block replacement policy, periodic preventive maintenance policy, failure limit policy, sequential preventive maintenance policy, repair cost limit policy, repair time limit policy, repair number counting policy, reference time policy, mixed age policy, group maintenance policy, opportunistic maintenance policy, etc. Each kind of policy has different characteristics, advantages and disadvantages with lot of contributions from Research scientist, Technologists... This survey summarizes, classifies, and compares various existing maintenance policies Around 170 Authors and their research works are presented in the Reference section. It will help to look into the different policies which is appropriate to the organization and for further study the reference section will be helpful for the researchers for further knowledge.

KEYWORDS

Maintenance policy; Maintenance; Reliability; Replacement; Optimization.

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OPEN STANDARDS AND OPEN SOURCE: ENABLING INTEROPERABILITY

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ABSTRACT

Interoperability is a major requirement for industries and governments in a society that increasingly moves towards global collaboration and integration. Open standards built on the principles of openness, transparency and consensus lay the grounds for innovation, growth and fair competition. Open standards are not synonymous of open source. The former is a set of specifications, the latter is an implementation. However, they share their commitment to openness and defend the equal opportunities of everyone to participate. This paper looks to the open source as the best way to enable interoperability between different technologies and applications. The role of open standards in interoperability is analyzed and some of the policies introduced by the European Union for the use and dissemination inside Members States are examined. Additionally, the use of open source software combined with open standards is presented and its major social benefits and economic impacts are highlighted.

KEYWORDS

Open Standards, Open Source, Interoperability, Software Development.

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